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The role of natural and artificial distraction in creating a sustainable environment for health institutions: Al-Sadr Teaching Hospital is a model

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Abstract

The research aims to benefit from the benefits and principles of natural and artificial shading inside buildings by reducing the harmful negative effects of the environment on health institutions, given that the dimensions and benefits of natural and artificial shading on the environment and the economic and social situation are directly related to achieving sustainability in line with the requirements of the times. The site of Al-Sadr Teaching Hospital, one of the health institutions in Najaf Governorate, was chosen as a model because it contains the required contrast in natural and artificial shading to test functional, sensory and environmental indicators on it and produce more results. This was done by collecting information from the field study of the hospital site, applying shading concepts to it, and determining the extent to which the principles of shading achieved comprehensiveness of the research. The results of the analysis of indicators of the components of the sensory experience showed clarity of space boundaries, ease of distinction and interconnection, clarity of the organizational principle, clarity of movement paths, abundance of directional signs, and clarity of the relationships between buildings and spaces, which in turn generates a feeling of individuals' ability to direct. The results also showed through the analysis of the formal components of space identity that it defines space by distinguishing visual elements and cues according to physical and non-physical characteristics, which constitute the basic criteria for the formal components of space identity.

key words: Natural and artificial shading, sustainable environment, health institution buildings.

Introduction:

The environmental and economic challenges that have cast their shadow on various sectors in this era, especially the urban aspect of our local environment, have led to the use of advanced planning and design methods and techniques that contribute to reducing the environmental impact and reducing operating and maintenance costs, they also contribute to providing a safe and comfortable urban environment to ensure its continuity, For the next generations. Ensuring the continuity of economic growth cannot be achieved in light of the threat to the environment with pollutants and waste and the destruction of its vital systems and thus the presence of an unsafe environment. For users. As well as the depletion of its natural resources, including water consumption, the increase in the amount of wastewater, the waste of building materials, and the environmental damage it causes to the land, plants, and air. The effects of urban activities and buildings on the environment have clear economic dimensions through excessive consumption of energy through reliance on artificial means and neglecting the

use of natural means. From (ventilation, lighting, etc.), this prompts the search for other sources that guarantee the continuity of compensation for these depleted sources that cannot be renewed. This is while proceeding in parallel in not wasting..

Research problem:

Does natural and artificial disinformation help create a sustainable environment in health institutions?

Research hypothesis:

Natural and artificial distractions play a role in creating a sustainable environment in health institutions.

Research aims:

- 1-Benefiting from the benefits and principles of natural and artificial shading inside buildings by reducing the harmful negative effects of the environment on health institutions.
- 2-The dimensions and benefits of natural and artificial shading on the environment and the economic and social

situation have a direct relationship to achieving sustainability in a way that is compatible with the requirements of the times.

Research Methodology:

The research relied on the structural approach to reach its objectives by sequentially listing the topics of the research, achieving its objectives, and then arriving at conclusions and recommendations for the research.

Boundaries of the search area:

The site of Al-Sadr Teaching Hospital was chosen because it contains the required contrast in natural and artificial shading to test its functional, sensory and environmental indicators and produce more comprehensive results about the research, map (1).

Search structure:The research consists of two sections:

The first topic:Discussing the concepts of natural and artificial shading, their definitions, and identifying the backgrounds behind their appearance And its dimensions and conclusion of its importance in different fields.

The second topic: The research dealt with the field study represented by one of the health institutions in Najaf Applying the concepts of shading to it in light of the concepts reached in the theoretical framework, collecting information from the field study of the area, and identifying the extent to which the principles of shading have been achieved there.

Map (1) Al-Sadr Teaching Hospital Source: Satellite image of AlSadr Teaching Hospital

The first topic

Concepts of natural and artificial shading

This research deals with the functional aspects of the integration of external building sites and their external spaces by addressing the spatial organization and its structural characteristics, the classification of external spaces based on the nature of functional performance, and clarifying the methods of organizing external spaces because of their impact on the nature of our perception of them. Space organization is the basis on which the process is based. Movement planning, in addition to being an important factor in the production of knowledge, is achieved by providing its basic requirements for patterns of encounter and isolation, which have been identified by recent studies and the material generators of social life. Health hospital sites require the highest environmental functional efficiency as they relate to human health, and this is achieved through global interest in the movement and visual systems of spaces Open.

First: The role of external organization in achieving functional coherence in the environment of health institutions:

Spaces should be designed to form a coherent framework for the spatial map of the urban environment and contribute to creating an institutional image that contains and contributes to increasing interaction by grading spaces and improving the environment within open spaces, as organizing urban spaces and preventing them from fragmentation is what gives their space a kind of vitality and efficiency. In the extent of occupancy, which is one of the most important features that must be provided to achieve integration between building sites and spaces. Space organization

stems from the basic characteristics:

* The property of symmetry - asymmetry:

It expresses the visual and kinetic depth of the various spaces of the urban environment relative to each other. The shallower the space is relative to other spaces, the greater its symmetry and vice versa.

Fourth: Environmental characteristics related to building blocks:

The building constructed on the site creates microclimatic conditions that differ from those conditions before its construction. These changes are mainly represented by a change in the exposure of the site's surfaces to solar radiation, a change in air movement within the site, and other subsequent changes such as a change in temperature and relative humidity. This change depends on the shape, size, and orientation of the block. A high building block (more than three floors) creates a change in the microclimate with a greater extent than the change caused by a low building block

The environmental characteristics of building blocks depend on several variables:

1. **Number of buildings:** Any building is often located within a group of buildings, so this building affects the rest of the neighboring buildings by moving air. As well as the extent of its exposure to solar radiation and humidity. When

• Diffusion property - asymmetry:

It expresses the choices of routes through the urban environment to reach all its spaces. The greater the number of ways to reach a particular space, the greater its spread in the urban environment and vice versa (1)

Second: Classification of outdoor spaces according to the nature of functional performance:

External spaces can be classified according to the nature of functional performance into:

- **Movement locations:** They are dynamic spaces that give a sense of movement and are unstable in nature. Usually in the form of a longitudinal strip that is relatively narrow with the rest of the spaces.
- **Stopping places:** These are stable spaces that give a feeling of comfort and stopping, and can be used for seating and wait.

Third: Methods of organizing outdoor spaces:

There are several ways of organizing spaces that affect the nature of our perception of them, and they can be summarized:

- **Linear organization:** that is, the presence of a linear sequence of successive spaces.
 - **Radial organization:** This means the presence of linear organizations of spaces extending radially from the central space Central.
 - **organization:** This means the presence of a dominant central space around which secondary spaces are gathered.
 - **cellular organization:** It means the presence of spaces that are close together and adjacent to each other because they share a common visual relationship or
 - **Feature Organization: Network:** It means the presence of organized spaces within the scope of a structural network.
- The functional organization of spaces has an impact on determining the number of individuals using it and is the basis on which the movement planning process is based. It depends on two types of use:
- **Primary use:** It represents the first point of attraction for space users.
 - **Secondary use:** includes secondary activities in outer space (2)

placing any block in the urban environment, a relationship will be generated with the spaces around it, and adding another block will make the relationship more complex. The presence of a number of adjacent buildings changes the extent of exposure of the site's surfaces to solar radiation and changes the behavior of the air, as the rate of wind will increase when a building is taller. (8 floors) and with a wide facade towards the wind to (160%) if there is a low building (consisting of two floors) in front of the first building at a distance equal to twice the height of the low building.

The percentage also increases to (200%) at the beginning of a tall building, and the number of buildings determines the size and boundaries of the space located between them and determines the degree of space closure and the method of grouping healthy buildings within the site. Therefore, the behavior of the air around several buildings may differ from its behavior around a building, but it depends on the same

principle in its movement as well as exposure to solar radiation affects temperature and relative humidity (3).

2.How to assemble buildings: The method of collection within the site affects the extent of exposure of the site's surfaces to solar radiation and also affects the behavior of the air in that site and the resulting effect on temperature

1. As for the winds following the outer lines above and around outer space (they do not penetrate it)
2. Or it penetrates it and generates air vortices near buildings. This behavior of air depends on several factors:
 - Outer space space.
 - Average height of surrounding buildings.
 - Opening width or the total width of openings between buildings.

3.Shape of buildings: Buildings control the extent of exposure to solar radiation, which creates shadow areas and affects the behavior of the air by directing the buildings and redirecting the movement of air around them. This affects

4. Orientation of buildings: The orientation of buildings directly affects the extent of exposure of outdoor spaces to radiation. The north-south orientation provides the possibility of less thermal variation compared to the east-west orientation. It has been found that the diagonal orientation provides greater shading potential than the north-south or east-west orientation and provides lower

5. Orientation of buildings: The orientation of buildings directly affects the extent of exposure of outdoor spaces to radiation. The north-south orientation provides the possibility of less thermal variation compared to the east-west orientation. It has been found that the diagonal orientation provides greater shading potential than the north-south or east-west orientation and provides lower temperatures. The orientation of buildings also affects the behavior of the wind and the distance of the air shadow area formed. Behind the building, when the angle between the wind movement and the longitudinal axis of the buildings is reduced, we notice that the depth of the air shadow distance will gradually decrease and reach its minimum if the building is parallel to the wind movement.

6. Connections between buildings: There are architectural parts that connect buildings together, such as roofs or spaces, with their design and natural components, are among the most important means used to reduce the impact of environmental factors, improve climatic conditions, and create conditions more suitable for human comfort, as it is the goal of design. Accordingly, studying the environmental impact of the design characteristics of outdoor spaces, as well as studying the natural contents of these spaces between the building sites.

Sixth: The environmental impact of the design characteristics of outdoor spaces:

The second topic

Field study (Al-Sadr Teaching Hospital)

In light of the analysis that was presented and the relationship between the functional, sensory, environmental and aesthetic aspects affecting the integrity of the site and its external spaces in accordance with the research problem, the research objective and its hypothesis, this chapter will focus on the practical study represented by measuring indicators and a general description of the selected environments, testing that data and then presenting it.

and humidity. The speed of the air decreases when it hits the building. If the wind is loaded with dust, the sudden change in air speed leads to the deposition of air particles and dust in the air shadow area. When buildings are connected to encircle space, the behavior of the air will be of two types:

the speed of the air and the pattern of air movement, which works to affect temperature and humidity. **It depends on:**

- ✓ The horizontal dimensions of buildings: Changing the horizontal dimensions of the building leads to a change in the depth of the air shadow area formed behind the building. When the length of the vertical façade in the direction of air movement increases, the width and depth of the air shadow area increases, while increasing the depth of the building (width) leads to reducing the depth of the air shadow area. Formed behind the building when the height and direction of air movement are constant.

temperatures. The orientation of buildings also affects the behavior of the wind and the distance of the air shadow area formed. Behind the building, when the angle between the wind movement and the longitudinal axis of the buildings is reduced, we notice that the depth of the air shadow distance will gradually decrease and reach its minimum if the building is parallel to the wind movement. (4)

porticoes, and they may be. These connections are from one side of the building or two sides. In some locations, there are no connections, and interconnection is one of the requirements of urban spaces, and it is an environmental relationship that meets the need

The links are of types:

- ✓ Roofings: They are horizontal flat surfaces that cover a specific area of the site's land and are located above a head level Human.
- ✓ Hallways: It is one of the environmental treatments in architecture. Its primary function is service, and it connects the different parts of the buildings in addition to their climatic characteristics.

Fifth: Environmental characteristics related to the external spaces between health building sites:

The design characteristics of the space greatly affect the environmental efficiency of the building block as a whole because the outer space will be a stage for convective heat exchange between the building blocks and the surrounding air. The temperature or microclimate elements that affect the thermal comfort of the user are solar radiation, temperature and wind. The natural forces that determine temperatures are solar radiation and wind, and this is reflected in humidity. Therefore, the environmental design of any site is done by controlling the exposure of various surfaces to solar radiation.

First: Indicators and measures:

1- Indicators of functional aspects.

Some of them are determined by the number (seating places, waste bins, kiosks), and the other part is determined by calculating their area (covers). The table shows the scale of the indicators of the components of outdoor spaces, Table (1).

Table (1) Indicators of functional aspects

the number/ thousand one lit	Seating places	Waste bins	Rooftops	Stalls	Evaluation		
	the number	the number	M2	the number	+	=	-
1	Nothing	12	560	Nothing			-
2	Nothing	7	300	Nothing			-
3	Nothing	6	240	Nothing			-
4	18	13	620	4	+		
5	12	8	430	3	+		

Source: researcher.

2- Sensory aspects indicators scale:

The formal components can be described through the formal components of the structure of outer space. They are evaluated through the method of observation and observation and through a set of attributes that have

been identified as in Table (2). The attributes that generate feelings are given a positive sign, and the attributes that generate negative feelings are indicated as negative attributes, and then given Final evaluation of the total attributes.

Table (2) Indicators of the formal components of outer space identity

Number External	Dependent Jah	the Location			degree			Alt Rate	
		relationship With vital centers	Signed On the line of movement	Possibility Vision remote					
					+	-			
1	Untreated With insulating material	+	+	-	46	32	14		-
2	Untreated With insulating material	+	+	-	45	32	13		-
3	Untreated With insulating material	+	+	-	45	32	13		-
4	Misleading natural	+	+	+	42	27	15	+	
5	Misleading natural	+	+	+	41	26	15	+	

Source: researcher.

3- Environmental aspects indicators scale:

Environmental indicators are measured by determining:
Number of buildings: Its purpose is to know and determine the size and boundaries of the space between them and

determine the degree of closure, thus determining the distance of the air shadow, as the distance of the air shadow depends on the length, width, and height of the building.

The method of assembling buildings depends on:

- ❖ space space

- ❖ Average space

- ❖ Slot width or the total width of slots between buildings

The shape of the buildings depends on the horizontal dimensions of the buildings and the height of the buildings.

4-Orienting buildings to the direction of the wind by determining the long axis in relation to the direction of the wind:

Table (3) Design characteristics indicators

N	Space shape	Space routing	Alt Rate	
			+	-
1	open	North South	+	
2	open	East West		-
3	open	North South	+	
4	Semi closed	East West		-
5	open	North South	+	

Source: researcher

Table (4) Indicators of external natural contents

N	kind of	Its density	Its location
1	Shrubbery	+	+
2	Shrubbery	+	+
3	Shrubbery	+	+
4	trees		+
5	trees		+

Source: Field study

Map (2)
Artificial deception areas

Map (3)
Areas of natural deception

Conclusions:

1. Paying attention to the integration of building sites and their external spaces is the main factor in creating a suitable and comfortable intellectual climate.
2. Providing appropriate outdoor spaces with all their elements and components is one of the basic goals that health institutions seek to achieve because of their importance in integrating the urban environment.
3. The design of outdoor spaces in health institutions consists of creating an environment suitable for functional use with the enjoyment that must be

- provided to individuals by creating an environment with a clear structure that expresses safety and beauty.
4. The design of outdoor spaces must meet the human need for social interaction, membership in groups, and his need for participation by attracting and encouraging people to gather, create social relationships, and increase interaction and meeting opportunities between them.
5. The successful performance of social outdoor spaces is considered one of the most important goals that the

designer seeks to achieve in planning outdoor spaces, so he must study the social influences in them.

6. The design of spaces in health institutions should provide opportunities for maximum possible interaction and communication between patients and affiliates and opportunities for random or planned meetings.

7. The results of analyzing the design variables of the relationship between space and the location of buildings highlighted the possibility of raising the value of the functional aspect of the spaces, thus increasing the efficiency of use by providing the number of motor 8. sectors, edges) and their connection with each other according to a clear organizational principle, which works to raise the value of the sensory aspect of the space.

9. The results of analyzing the formal components of space identity highlighted that space is defined by distinguishing elements and visual cues according to physical and non-physical characteristics, which constitute basic criteria for the formal components of space identity.

10. The results of the analysis of the indicators of the components of the sensory experience revealed that the clarity of the boundaries of space, the ease of

outlets and new axes, reducing the visual outlets of the space, and creating diverse relationships between the blocks.

11. The results were highlighted by analyzing the components of the designed complements, which work to raise the value of the functional aspect of the space.

12. The results of the analysis of the formal components of the space highlighted the agreement and harmony of the five elements of the structure (paths, nodes, landmarks,

distinguishing it and its interconnectedness, the clarity of the organizational principle, the clarity of movement paths, the abundance of indicative signs, and the clarity of the relationships between buildings and spaces, in turn generate some sense of the ability to direct individuals.

Recommendations.

1. Preparing new designs for urban spaces.
2. Expansion and development of urban space components
3. Improving and developing the external spaces of health institutions
4. Compare design alternatives to choose the best.

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